

A0215

TiO_xN_y based protective coatings for corrosion protection of 316L stainless steel bipolar plates under PEM water electrolyzer-like conditions

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Abstract

Proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers (PEMWE) electrochemically split the water molecules in order to produce high-purity oxygen (at the anode) and hydrogen (at the cathode). The elevated capital expenditures (capex) deriving from the use of expensive corrosion-resistant materials undermine the economic competitiveness of this technology [1]. In this contribution, we will focus on the corrosion protection of anodic 316L bipolar plates with titanium oxynitride (TiO_xN_y) thin films. The thin coatings, including TiO_xN_y/Ti/TiO_xN_y multilayer, were grown by reactive magnetron sputtering and characterized by X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, transmission electron microscopy, atomic force microscopy, X-ray reflectivity, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, electron energy loss spectroscopy and interfacial contact resistance measurements. The multilayer design demonstrated improved interfacial contact resistance compared to single-layer coatings. The corrosion resistance of both TiO_xN_y and TiO_xN_y/Ti/TiO_xN_y - coated stainless steel, was evaluated *ex situ* using open-circuit potential monitoring and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy in dilute H₂SO₄ solution in a three-electrode electrochemical cell at 60°C.

[1] M. Prestat, Corrosion of structural components of proton exchange membrane water electrolyzer anodes: A review, J. Power Sourc. 556 (2023) 232469.

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the French National Research Agency (agreement ANR-22-PEHY-0009 under the France 2030 program and agreement ANR-22-CE93-0008-01).

1. Introduction

Water electrolysis, in particular proton exchange membrane electrolysis (PEMWE), is a key technology for producing clean hydrogen. It is based on the use of an electric current to dissociate water into oxygen and hydrogen. This process requires components capable of withstanding an acidic, oxidising environment and temperatures of up to 60°C. Among these components, bipolar plates (BPPs) play a crucial role in the efficiency and durability of the electrolyzer. They ensure uniform distribution of the reactive gases over the electrodes, which in turn ensures optimum cell performance [2]. Today, BPPs are mainly made of titanium, a material chosen for its resistance to corrosion. However, titanium has two major limitations. It is expensive and oxidizes under PEMWE conditions, resulting in increased interfacial contact resistance (ICR) and degradation in cell performance [3] [4] [5]. To limit this degradation, noble metals such as platinum are used as protective coatings. These materials offer excellent chemical stability but significantly increase production costs. This additional cost directly affects the capital expenditure (CAPEX) associated with PEMWE technology and undermines its competitiveness. It is estimated that BPPs account for around 50% of the total cost of a stack [2]. To overcome these limitations, several studies have turned to the use of stainless steel, in particular 316L, as a possible alternative. This material is less expensive, easy to machine and available on a large scale. However, it offers inadequate corrosion resistance in PEMWE environments, due to the progressive dissolution of the passive oxide that forms naturally on its surface. To improve its chemical durability, many studies have focused on the application of protective coatings. Several approaches are proposed in the literature, mainly based on ceramic or metallic coatings. Coatings based on nitrides (TiN, CrN) [6] [7] and metallic bilayer (Ti/Pt, Ti/Nb) [8] [9] are cited for their stability in acidic media and good electrical conductivity.

The present work aims at studying the chemical stability of TiO_xN_y and TiO_xN_y/Ti/TiO_xN_y coatings on 316L stainless steel substrate produced by magnetron sputtering. Among the numerous deposited coatings, we focus here on the TiO_xN_y coated steel. Structural characterizations (X-Ray Diffraction, Atomic Force Microscopy) were carried out on the coating to assess its crystallinity and morphology. We subsequently evaluated the corrosion resistance of TiO_xN_y coated SS 316L in near-neutral solution (sulfuric acid pH 4) at the Open Circuit Potential (OCP) and at 60°C to mimic the operating conditions of BPPs on the anodic side of the PEMWE [1]. The stability of the coating was studied by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Coating deposition process:

TiO_xN_y thin films were deposited using the DC reactive magnetron sputtering method, employing a high-purity 3" Ti target (99.999%). In this study, as-received 316L stainless steel (50 x 50 x 2 mm³) and silicon wafer (Si) were used as substrates. Before deposition, the substrates were cleaned with ultrasonication in acetone and ethanol and rinsed with deionized water. Ti target was facing the substrate at a working distance of about 70 mm. Before the sputtering process, the deposition chamber was evacuated to a base pressure of 1 x 10⁻⁷ mbar. The deposition was carried out with a mixture of high-purity Ar and N₂ reactive gases. To induce plasma during the growth process, a DC voltage with a total power of 75 W was applied to the target. The depositions were carried out in the sputtering chamber, as shown in Figure 1, where the plasma can be seen during the process.

Figure1. View of the plasma inside the sputtering chamber during the deposition process.

The deposition time varied between 5 and 60 minutes during the sputtering process to produce TiO_xN_y coatings in the 20-200 nm thickness range. Film thickness was measured using a mechanical profilometer. Surface topography was analyzed by atomic force microscopy (AFM) to assess deposit roughness and homogeneity. The crystalline structure of the coatings was determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD), to identify the phases present and verify the crystallinity of the deposited layers.

2.2. Electrochemical testing:

Electrochemical study was conducted using an Orignalys potentiostat system. A three-electrode double-jacket cell was designed to perform this experiment, which contained approximately 90 ml of diluted H₂SO₄ at pH 4. To maintain a stable temperature of 60°C, a thermostatic bath (LAUDA) was used. Platinum-coated titanium and hydrogen electrodes were used as counter electrode (CE) and reference electrode (RE), respectively. The uncoated and TiO_xN_y-coated SS 316L investigated in this study were used as working electrodes (WE). The sample was immersed in the solution for one hour to obtain equilibrium potential, and the electrochemical impedance was measured under these conditions. The data were recorded using an excitation voltage of 10 mV over a 104 to 0.003 Hz frequency range.

3. Results

Grazing angle XRD (GI-XRD) measurements were conducted on TiO_xN_y films grown on Si with different thicknesses, as illustrated in Figure 2. The thickness of the films and deposition times are also indicated in the figure. Diffraction patterns corresponding to the (200) and (220) reflection of the face-centered cubic (f.c.c.) phase are observed for the films with thicknesses higher than 58 nm. This highlights the polycrystalline nature of the coating. Note that the films with a thickness less than 58 nm do not show any diffraction pattern.

Figure 2: GI-XRD patterns of three different TiO_xN_y single-layers compared.

It can be seen that the width of peak associated to the (220) diffraction pattern decreases with increasing film thickness, a phenomenon associated with an increase of the grain. This size (D) can be determined from the FWHM using the Debye-Scherrer equation:

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta_{(hkl)}} \quad (1)$$

Where λ is the wavelength of the radiation (in the present case, $\lambda = 0.15418$ nm), β is the full width at half maxima (FWHM) of the peak measured at the angle associated with the (200) direction. The grain size of (200) crystallites increases from 13.7 to 17.6 nm as the thickness increases. This behavior is explained by the aggregation of small grains, which is consistent with the findings of Hailong et al. [10].

Figures 3 (a) and (b) show the AFM topography of TiO_xN_y films deposited on Si, with thicknesses of 22 and 200 nm respectively. These images, acquired in tapping mode over a 500 nm x 500 nm scan area, reveal a clear increase in grain size from 13 to 19 nm with increasing film thickness, confirming the XRD results. This image also highlights the low roughness (Rq) of TiO_xN_y films, increasing from 0.6 to 2 nm as thickness increases from 22 to 200 nm.

Figure 3 : AFM topographic images of (a) 22 nm- TiO_xN_y and (b) 200 nm- TiO_xN_y deposited on silicon substrates.

In order to evaluate the protective properties of the TiO_xN_y coating, a thickness of 200 nm was selected for electrochemical testing to ensure a complete coverage of the stainless steel surface. As a first step, uncoated SS 316L was exposed to a diluted H₂SO₄ solution at pH 4, maintained at OCP and 60°C over 7 days. The impedance curves measured during this period are shown in Figures 4(a,b). An increase of the impedance was observed at low frequencies, which is generally associated with growth of the passive layer. This passive layer is not desirable for BPPs, as it leads to an increase in interfacial contact resistance (ICR), resulting in a loss of electrolyzer performance [4] [5]. As seen in Fig. 4(a,b), the impedance variation mainly occurs during the first 62h of exposure. Fig. 4(c) displays the OCP variation. An increase of the OCP is also observed during the first hours of exposure, in agreement with a passive layer formation. Figures 5(a,b) display the Bode plots recorded for coated steel. In contrast, for 316L stainless steel coated with 200 nm-TiO_xN_y, the impedance remains stable throughout the 7 days of immersion. These results highlight the effectiveness of the TiO_xN_y film in protecting 316L steel from the growth of the passive layer. The coated steel shows a slightly higher OCP (figure 5 (c)) than the uncoated steel (figure 5(c)) indicating a reduced electrochemical activity.

Figure 4: Electrochemical investigation of uncoated 316L in diluted H₂SO₄ solution (pH = 4) at 60°C for 7 days. (a,b) Bode plots; (c) open circuit potential.

Figure 5: Electrochemical investigation of 200 nm-TiO_xN_y coated SS 316L in diluted H₂SO₄ solution (pH = 4), at the OCP and 60°C. (a,b) Bode plots, (c) open circuit potential

4. Conclusion

To reduce the cost of hydrogen production, this study investigates the use of 200 nm-TiO_xN_y magnetron sputtered coating on SS 316L BPP as an alternative to precious metal-coated titanium BPPS. The results show that uncoated SS 316L exhibits a surface passivation after exposure to pH 4 at OCP and 60°C. On the other hand, TiO_xN_y coating shows a good stability after exposure to the same conditions, making it suitable for use as a coating of SS 316L BPP for PEM electrolyser. Additional tests, including other pH conditions are in progress and will be presented at the conference.

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Keywords: *EFCF2025, H₂, Low-Temp. Fuel Cells & Electrolysers, Water electrolysis, Bipolar plate, Coating, Stainless steel, Titanium oxynitride.*

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